

ASSESSING THE FACTORS AFFECTING BUYING BEHAVIOR IN SERVICE SECTOR

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ABSTRACT

By definition, demographic segmentation divides a market into subsets defined by characteristics like age, gender, income, etc. Companies need to be in tune and up to date with the ever-evolving market conditions, therefore demographic segmentation plays a significant role in the development and rollout of both existing and new products and services. Although a sizable minority of people now utilise banking and financial services, winning over this group will be a significant challenge for the banking sector. The purpose of this study is to investigate and analyse customer reaction to new product or service offerings and how demographic subgroups within a population respond to such changes. The primary data came from a survey of 350 people in Kolkata. Cronbach's Alpha was used to check the consistency of the data and analysis of variance was used to evaluate the hypotheses. Using ANOVA, we investigated the hypothesis that there would be a significant variation in the respondents' customer behaviour based on their demographic characteristics, and we discovered no such difference.

Keywords: *Relevant Keywords: Consumer Behavior, Investment Management, Demography, Market Dynamics*

INTRODUCTION

Since population changes over time, marketers can't just get static demographic information once and utilise it forever. Every year, we get brand new census numbers. For a complete and accurate picture, this data must be collected continuously. A robust financial system is essential for a country's progress. The banking industry is crucial to the progress of a country like India, which has a population of over 135 million people. Of India's 1.3 billion people, over half are younger than 25 and over 65 percent are younger than 35. Projections for 2020 indicate that the median age of a native Indian will be 29. After launching the Jan-Dhan Yojna, the government has made consistent efforts to encourage everyone to get a bank account. Even while most people have become accustomed to using ATMs, a sizable minority remains inactive in banking, making it difficult for financial institutions to win over the public's trust. A.J. "Molly" P. "Koshy" Joshua Since the economic reforms and the inclusion of private companies alongside public sector banks, India's banking sector has played an increasingly vital role in the progress of our country

(Ambuj Gupta). The world's banking services can be broken down into two broad categories: investment banking and industrial banking. Since their nationalisation in 1969, most banks have been under the control of the Indian government, with the Reserve Bank of India serving as the country's apex financial institution. There has been a dramatic movement in banking sector consumers from public sector banks to private sector banks since the advent of private companies in the industry in 1991. This makes the quality of service these banks give a crucial factor in determining which ones succeed and which ones fail. CASA, internet banking, retail banking, financial consulting, locker facilities, international money transfers, and much more are just some of the services offered by the banks today. E-banking and the adoption of cutting-edge technology are helping to supplant the traditional banking system, and banks are working tirelessly to attract and retain consumers and satisfy them to an even greater degree than before. (Dr.G.Karthikeyan). More and more delighted customers are the top priority for all banks, whether they are government-owned or privately owned. Consumers in the modern day have their pick of many different banking services, and banks work hard to gauge customers' opinions on the quality of such services. Today's banking institutions must overcome scepticism about their products and services from clients if they are to thrive. This can be done only by fostering a trusting relationship with their clientele and meeting their needs through a wide range of useful products and services.

AN EVALUATION OF SERVICE QUALITY IN RELATION TO CUSTOMER ACTIONS

The term "service quality" refers to how well a service satisfies a clientele's requirements or anticipations. As the final arbiter of the service's worth, the customer's perspective on the outcome and delivery method is paramount in any evaluation of the service's quality.

The five factors that make up a high-quality service are as follows:

Among the quality dimensions, reliability has been found to have the greatest impact on how customers react. It's being able to adjust how you provide the protected service without sacrificing accuracy or dependability.

Second, responsiveness refers to the employees' eagerness to help clients and provide them with timely results. Customers' attention is likely to wane if the service is late.

Thirdly, assurance refers to the service provider's ability to instil confidence and trust in the service's recipients. If potential clients have faith in the company, they'll see it favourably.

An organization's ability to empathise with its clients' experiences is a key differentiator in the service industry. The service provider can gain a better understanding of the customer's perspective if he puts himself in the customer's position. A satisfactory level of satisfaction for

many clients is reached when they perceive that the provider has made an honest attempt to understand their point of view.

Tangibles: This term describes a company's outward appearance, including its buildings, machinery, and employees. Physical evidence of a service's existence serves multiple purposes. A patient in the waiting area of a clinic can gauge the kind of care he might expect to receive by looking at the doctor's credentials. Customer confidence in the quality of the service can be increased by providing tangible examples of it..

THE IMPORTANCE OF THIS RESEARCH

Of India's 1.3 billion people, over half are younger than 25 and over 65 percent are younger than 35. The median age of an Indian is projected to be 29 by the year 2020, and as more and more financial institutions open shop in the country, it will be crucial for such institutions to differentiate themselves from the competition if they hope to thrive and turn a profit. Providing high-quality service has become increasingly important in the banking business as clients have more options for where they can conduct financial transactions. The success or failure of a service provider is ultimately determined by the quality of service as experienced and perceived by its customers over time. A happy client will spread the word and a disgruntled one will hurt business. Perceptions of these services as a whole become a crucial variable in determining consumer happiness.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Rokeach (1973) discusses 30 values total—18 terminal values and 18 instrumental values—in his methodology, the Rokeach Value Survey (RSV). The RVS approach is the primary basis for Prakash's (1986) discussion of women's market segmentation by value structure. Using numerous segmentation criteria to zero in on smaller, more precisely defined sub-markets where your firm can shine is a strategy advocated by Chin-Feng Lin (2002). Haemoon Oh, While differences between young and elderly travellers may be apparent at the attribute and multivariate construct levels, Sara C. Parks and Frederick J. Demicco (2002) contend that these differences cannot be explained by differences in how each group processes information in its entirety. Geographic segmentation, demographic segmentation, psychographic segmentation, and behavioural segmentation are some of Shili Sun's (2009) suggested starting points for dividing up the consumer market or the business market. Using these criteria, companies can better target their marketing efforts by identifying certain niches in the market.

Although differences between young and elderly travellers were found at the attribute and multivariate construct levels, these differences were not found at the level of how information was processed in its whole. Both sexes were free to draw the same conclusions. This is reassuring because it suggests that it is worthwhile for marketers to establish general theories of consumer choice that can account for the needs of both types of consumers. In their study,

Kordshouli Younes Jafarpour and Ahmad Allahyari Bouzanjani (2016) argued that the dimensions of service quality have a positive effect on customer satisfaction and aimed to fill a gap in the literature by investigating the relationship between customers' perceptions of service quality and their altruistic actions. According to Prof. V.Narasimha Rao and Smt. M.B. Suvarchala (2018), banking consumers' attitudes and behaviours have shifted significantly over the past several years. Due to the public's lack of familiarity with digital payments, businesses are vulnerable to threats like cyber fraud. In his study, Jignesh Valand (2016) discusses the modifications service providers need to make in terms of offering, education attitudes and snapshots, advertising and marketing strategies in the organisation that will meet the expectations and help them to recognise who their customers are, what they select, what they purchase, who makes the purchasing decisions, and how the customers use merchandise and service to influence their attitudes toward the banks and the service providers. To: Prof. G. Thangapandi K. Gobinath's (2016) study found that banks may benefit from concentrating on client pooling and retention if they did so. The bank-customer connection can benefit from making the customer feel like he or she is an important cog in the machine. The banks need to focus their efforts where they can best increase brand value. According to research conducted by Koushiki Choudhry (2007), clients in India's retail banking industry value four aspects of service quality: friendliness, knowledge, responsiveness, and ease of doing business. The first step in defining and providing quality service in India's retail banking system is identifying the underlying elements of the service quality construct.

Using data from the dimensions of service quality, this study argues that bank management will implement measures to improve their staff's competence and attitude toward customers. Based on the findings of Sandip Gosh Hasra and BL Srivastava's (2009) research, the bank should prioritise the assurance-empathy dimension of service quality if it wants to increase customer loyalty, payment commitment, commitment to the brand, and trust. Researchers Joshua A.J. and Moli.P.Koshi(2005) found that new generation banks perform better than old generation banks in every metric of service quality. An alternate scale for gauging customers' opinions of their retail banking experiences was proposed by Bahia and Nantel (2000). When comparing BSQ dimensions to SERVQUAL, the researchers determined that the former were more trustworthy.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

To study the impact of demographic factors on customer buying behavior

HYPOTHESIS

H1: There is a significant impact of demographic factors on customer buying behavior

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Three hundred and fifty participants from all around the Kolkata area provided the raw data for the study. In order to investigate how customers feel about the banking options now available to them, a thorough questionnaire targeting residents of the Kolkata metropolitan area was developed. A 5-point Likert scale was used to compile the responses.

DATA ANALYSIS

Table 1. Demographics profile of the customers

Variable	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	292	83
	Female	58	17
Age Group	20 – 30	42	12
	30 - 40	44	13
	40 - 50	124	35
	Above 50	140	40
Education	SSC	14	4
	HSC	114	32
	Graduate	178	51
	Post Graduate	44	13
Occupation	Student	18	5
	Salaried	224	64
	Self employed	100	29
	Not working	8	2
Yearly Income	Below Rs. 250000	102	29
	Rs. 250000-500000	94	27
	Rs. 500000-750000	130	37
	Above Rs. 750000	24	7

The demographics of a representative cross-section of the population who make use of banking services for commercial purposes are shown in Table 1. Males make up 83% of the respondents, while females account for 17%. The majority (93%) of the sample population has a salaried job in either the private or public sector; 51% have completed college while 13% have completed graduate school; 88% are adults over the age of 30; and 61% earn between 250000 and 750000 rupees annually, making them a prime demographic for the banking system.

RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY

Cronbach's alpha, a measure of internal consistency, is presented in table 2 below. Examination of the reliability of the survey's various rating systems. When the Cronbach's Alpha is 1, we know that the data is completely reliable. In this example, the score of 0.842 indicates that the

data is reliable and the test could be carried out, surpassing the usually accepted cutoff of 0.7 for the reliability of data including customer behaviour when using banks for transactions.

Table 1: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.842	16

Finding Data from a poll of 350 people of varying ages, sexes, professions, levels of education, and incomes have been subjected to a frequency analysis in an effort to understand respondents' behaviours and their level of satisfaction.

Those who highly agree and agree are the most vital, whereas those who strongly disagree and disagree are less crucial when it comes to bolstering the pleasure and behaviour of responders. Those who responded with a neutral behaviour neither favoured nor opposed the characteristics.

Table 2: Frequency Analysis

Attributes	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Convenience of branch location	68	0	238	40	4
Service Facilities	108	152	62	24	4
Reliability of the employees	94	130	68	44	14
Overall Service Standard	100	74	96	48	32
Service Charges	108	56	82	80	24
Responsiveness	78	56	90	100	26
Level of Professionalism of the Employees	74	68	84	114	10
Empathy towards the customers	68	56	92	104	30
Speed of Transaction	84	40	84	94	48

According to the data presented above, the vast majority of respondents are satisfied with the quality of services provided by the banking system, while just a small percentage of consumers have expressed dissatisfaction.

CONCLUSION

The purpose of this research was to examine the impact of demographic segmentation parameters on the many features of the banking sector. The data reliability test found an 84.2 percent success rate, and further frequency analysis revealed that the vast majority of respondents viewed the quality of banking services as good, with only a minority of consumers expressing dissatisfaction. Customers' growing awareness of the importance of demography, and the potential it has to inform their purchasing decisions, has prompted businesses to reevaluate their marketing strategies in light of the new market realities.

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